

FORMATION OF MOTIVATION OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY OF SCHOOL CHILDREN IN TECHNOLOGY LESSONS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the use of methods and techniques of modern pedagogical technologies in educational activities to positively motivate children, the use of a system of creative tasks to develop students' motivation for learning activities, the successful formation of positive motives.

Motive is the key to every person's work. He acts as an "energy battery" of the personality, and the intensity of a person's work depends on his strength. Each appeal to the psychology of personality, for example, or in another way highlights the basic meaning of the motivational soil of work. There is no internal motive - an internal driving force, and every business is doomed to be tedious, sour, worthless.

Motives (interests, necessities, drives, beliefs, standards, impressions, passions, instincts, attitudes) are actually what inspires a person to work, because of what it is done. The internal motive of educational activity should always precede and accompany learning. The motivation of teaching is not a spontaneous process, and it would be rash and hopeless to rely here only on natural inclinations. Motivation should be specially formed, developed, stimulated. The process of formation and consolidation of positive motives of

educational activity in students is called motivation of educational activity. The main factors influencing the formation of positive motivation for learning activities are:

1. The content of the educational material.
2. The communication style of the teacher and students.
3. The nature and level of educational and cognitive activity.

The result of the work in this direction was the adjustment of programs and planning documentation, taking into account the factors influencing the formation of positive motivation. The curricula have been adjusted to take into account the interest of students. The content of the perspective-thematic plan on the subject has been revised, revised in terms of the selection of various types of independent work, the improvement of didactic material, a variety of teaching tools that increase the effectiveness of training. The

selection of the content of educational material for lessons is also carried out taking into account the fact that the information should be interesting and understandable for students. The assignment should be selected taking into account the psychophysiological characteristics of the students. The structure of the lesson provides for a timely change of activities in order to maintain students' interest in the material being studied. For clarity, various didactic materials, natural samples, patterns and mini-patterns are used in the classroom. New modern materials and technologies. Also, information and computer technologies should be used in the lesson:

1. Printed materials using electronic media (instruction cards, didactic material)
2. Fragments of the lesson are used on disks.
3. Have a presentation of the lesson using multimedia.

The formation of teaching motives is influenced by the style of pedagogical activity, relationships with students. In terms of learning and relationships with students, an important role is played by:

1. Showing achievements and shortcomings in the development of personality, showing confidence in the strengths and capabilities of students.
2. The manifestation of the personal attitude of the teacher to the student, the group, the expression of his own opinion.
3. The teacher's manifestation of his own qualities, personality data (in terms of communication, erudition, attitude to the subject, business qualities, etc.) and encouraging students to such manifestations.

4. Organization of friendly relations in the team (mutual verification, exchange of opinions, mutual assistance).

There is a wide choice of forms and methods of stimulating and motivating cognitive activity. Conditionally, we can distinguish 4 blocks of the main methods of motivation: emotional, cognitive, volitional and social.

Emotional encouragement, censure, educational and cognitive game, Educational reliance on life experience, cognitive interest, creating a problem situation,

III. Volitional

presentation of educational requirements, informing about mandatory learning outcomes,

forming a responsible attitude to learning,

IV. Social

development of the desire to be useful to society,

the urge to imitate a strong personality, creating a situation of mutual assistance,

The system of creative tasks for the development of motivation for learning activities is a set that includes creative tasks with interesting content from three main groups:

- 1) cause-and-effect relationships,
- 2) combining information,
- 3) planning and implementation of practical activities.

The use of a system of creative tasks to develop students' motivation for learning activities involves the use of at least one task from each group in each lesson.

Such an approach to the problem of motivation development requires time, but above all a creative approach to their

activities. This is possible when mastering a new pedagogical thinking, when rethinking and revising the technology of work, with systematic creative growth.

The principle of recruiting students when recruiting small groups is of great motivational importance. If children with neutral motivation for a subject are combined with children who do not like

this subject, then after working together, the former significantly increase their interest in this subject. The use of methods and techniques of modern pedagogical technologies in educational activities forms positive motivation of children, promotes the development of basic mental operations, communicative competence, creative active personality.

References:

1. Dubovitskaya, T. D. Methodology for diagnosing the orientation of educational motivation, T. D. Dubovitskaya Psychological science and education. - 2002.
2. Gerasimova, A. S. Theory of educational motivation in Russian psychology A. S. Gerasimova Institute of Psychology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Gorsky, V. A. Technological training of schoolchildren in the field of additional education V. A. Gorsky.
3. Dyuzheva, O. A. Pedagogical conditions for the formation of educational motivation of schoolchildren O. A. Dyuzheva. - Kostroma, 2010.